

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Adaptive Algebra Instruction: Effects on Students' Self-Efficacy and Problem-Solving Skills in Northern Nigeria

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This quasi-experimental study investigated the impact of Squirrel AI, an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive learning platform, on senior secondary school students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in algebra in Northern Nigeria. The study employed a pre-test and post-test control-group design using intact classes. A total of 180 Senior Secondary II students from four public co-educational secondary schools in Zaria Education Zone of Kaduna State participated, with 90 students in each of the experimental and control groups. The experimental group received instruction through the Squirrel AI platform, which adapts learning pathways by diagnosing students' misconceptions, adjusting content difficulty, and providing real-time feedback, while the control group was taught using conventional lecture methods. Two instruments were used for data collection: the Algebra Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES) and the Algebra Problem-Solving Test (APST). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Results revealed that students in the experimental group recorded significantly higher self-efficacy and problem-solving scores than those in the control group, with large effect sizes (partial $\eta^2 = 0.180$ and 0.298 , respectively). These findings underscore the transformative potential of AI-powered instruction in enhancing mathematics outcomes in resource-limited contexts such as Northern Nigeria, where infrastructural challenges and educational disparities often hinder student achievement. The study concludes by recommending the integration of AI tools into the Nigerian secondary school curriculum and teacher training programs to foster personalized, data-driven, and equitable learning opportunities in mathematics.

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Adaptive Learning, Self-Efficacy, Problem-Solving, Algebra Instruction, Secondary School Mathematics, Educational Technology

Introduction

In the 21st century, the integration of technology into education has become a cornerstone of instructional innovation, particularly in mathematics, where abstract concepts often pose significant challenges for learners. Algebra, a foundational branch of mathematics, is pivotal in developing

students' analytical reasoning, problem-solving ability, and preparation for advanced STEM fields. However, in many parts of Northern Nigeria, secondary school students continue to experience persistent difficulties in understanding and applying algebraic concepts effectively (Eneze et al., 2020).

These challenges are compounded by overcrowded classrooms, insufficient instructional resources, and limited teacher capacity, alongside a one-size-fits-all teaching approach that fails to accommodate individual learning needs.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a promising solution to these challenges by enabling adaptive instruction a method that adjusts the difficulty, pacing, and content of lessons to fit learners' performance in real time (Yambal & Waykar, 2025). Unlike conventional methods, AI-powered systems analyze student responses, diagnose misconceptions, and provide customized feedback, thereby enhancing mastery of concepts and promoting independent learning. International studies have shown that such systems increase engagement, reduce cognitive overload, and improve learning outcomes (Gupta et al., 2021).

Despite these advancements globally, there remains a notable research gap in Northern Nigeria regarding the application and effectiveness of AI-based learning platforms in secondary schools. Prior studies in the region have largely focused on traditional instructional innovations, with minimal attention to adaptive technologies. In particular, the impact of AI tools on students' self-efficacy their belief in their capability to learn and solve problems—and on their algebraic problem-solving performance has not been adequately investigated. Bandura (1997) emphasized that self-efficacy influences academic persistence, motivation, and success in complex reasoning tasks such as algebra. Moreover, the Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1994) suggests that adaptive learning systems, by tailoring instruction to individual learners, can reduce extraneous cognitive load and optimize

working memory, thereby improving both confidence and performance.

Therefore, this study investigates how AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction influences students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in selected secondary schools across Northern Nigeria. By focusing on these two critical variables, the research aims to provide evidence-based insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers on the transformative role of AI in mathematics education, particularly in resource-constrained environments where infrastructural limitations and educational disparities persist.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized importance of algebra in secondary school mathematics and its central role in fostering logical reasoning and problem-solving abilities, students in many schools across Northern Nigeria continue to demonstrate low proficiency and poor attitudes toward the subject. Reports from examination bodies such as WAEC and NECO (2023) consistently reveal that a significant proportion of candidates fail to display both conceptual understanding and procedural fluency in algebraic tasks. This persistent underperformance has been linked to the dominance of traditional teacher-centered instructional strategies, which often ignore learners' individual differences and cognitive needs (Ghaleb, 2024).

Conventional teaching approaches, particularly the chalk-and-talk or lecture method, rarely accommodate the varied learning paces, prior knowledge, and engagement styles of students. As a result, many learners experience mathematics anxiety and a sense of helplessness when

confronted with algebraic problems, leading to reduced self-efficacy and avoidance behaviors (Zuo et al., 2024). Research has shown that low self-efficacy in mathematics strongly predicts weak problem-solving performance, as students are less likely to attempt, persist with, or complete challenging tasks.

Recent advancements in educational technology have introduced Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven adaptive learning platforms as a potential solution to these challenges. Such systems can dynamically adjust instructional content in response to learner input, providing real-time feedback, targeted scaffolding, and differentiated support to promote mastery learning. However, while AI applications in education are gaining global recognition, their pedagogical potential remains underutilized and under-researched in Nigeria, particularly in rural and underserved areas of the North.

Specifically, there is insufficient empirical evidence on how AI-powered adaptive learning systems influence students' self-efficacy and algebraic problem-solving skills in the Nigerian secondary school context. Most existing local studies have concentrated on general e-learning tools or computer-assisted instruction without investigating the unique affordances of AI's adaptive capabilities. This creates a pressing need for context-specific research on the transformative potential of AI in mathematics classrooms.

Therefore, this study seeks to bridge the gap by investigating whether the integration of AI-based adaptive algebra instruction can strengthen students' confidence in their mathematical abilities and enhance their problem-solving performance. The findings

are expected to contribute to educational research and practice by providing empirical insights into the effectiveness of AI-powered instruction in resource-constrained contexts. Ultimately, the study aims to inform the shift toward more personalized, data-driven, and equitable learning approaches capable of improving mathematics outcomes across secondary schools in Northern Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive algebra instruction on senior secondary school students' self-efficacy and problem-solving skills in Northern Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to:

Determine the effect of AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction on students' self-efficacy in algebra. To Examine the impact of AI-powered adaptive instruction on students' algebraic problem-solving performance.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

- What is the difference in self-efficacy scores between students who taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those who taught using conventional methods?
- What is the difference in algebraic problem-solving performance between students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught through conventional methods?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy scores of students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Review of Related Literature

Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) has emerged as a transformative force, offering systems that can personalize learning experiences and provide real-time feedback. Adaptive learning technologies utilize AI algorithms to adjust instructional pathways based on student performance, thereby enhancing individualized support and engagement (Gligorea et al., 2023). These systems collect and analyze data from learners' interactions—such as time spent on tasks, patterns of errors, and response accuracy to deliver tailored content, scaffolded hints, and strategic challenges (Liu et al., 2024). By continuously adapting instruction to learners' evolving needs, AI holds significant promise for mathematics education.

Algebraic problem solving, a key component of the secondary mathematics curriculum, requires conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, and strategic competence. Unfortunately, many Nigerian students struggle with algebra due to its abstract nature, limited contextualization, and reliance on rote instruction (Julius, 2025). When teaching methods fail to consider learners' developmental stages or diverse learning needs, their problem-solving performance declines. Adaptive AI tools offer a potential remedy by personalizing

instruction and providing feedback that supports mastery at an individual pace.

Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy as an individual's belief in their capacity to execute tasks and reach goals. In mathematics, self-efficacy strongly influences students' choices, persistence, and *resilience* when faced with challenging tasks. AI-powered instruction has been found to enhance self-efficacy by creating low-stakes environments in which learners receive immediate feedback, monitor their progress, and build confidence as they gradually overcome difficulties (Abdelhalim & Alsehibany, 2025).

This study is anchored in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), particularly the construct of self-efficacy, and Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988). According to Social Cognitive Theory, learning is shaped by the interaction of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. When students believe they can succeed, they are more likely to engage meaningfully and persist. Cognitive Load Theory complements this by highlighting how adaptive systems reduce extraneous cognitive load and manage intrinsic task complexity, thereby improving working memory efficiency during problem-solving. Together, these theories justify the potential of AI-powered adaptive instruction in algebra.

A growing body of empirical literature supports the effectiveness of adaptive AI tools in mathematics education. Cho & Kim (2025) found that students who used AI-based personalized learning platforms in algebra demonstrated higher achievement compared to peers taught through conventional methods. Alkhasawneh (2025) similarly reported that intelligent tutoring

systems improved student engagement and accuracy in solving equations. In Africa, Abdulazeez et al., (2024) studied computer-assisted instruction in Kwara State and observed significant improvements in students' motivation and performance, even though the tools were not fully AI-driven. Likewise, Ibrahim and Özcan (2024) showed that step-by-step adaptive hints enhanced students' algebraic problem-solving strategies.

However, critiques of AI in education caution against over-reliance on technology, highlighting challenges such as infrastructural gaps, inequitable access, digital literacy limitations, and possible resistance from teachers unfamiliar with adaptive systems (Aliyu et al., 2025). Moreover, much of the empirical research has been conducted in urban or well-resourced schools, leaving limited evidence from rural or resource-constrained contexts where educational challenges are often most acute.

Despite these limitations, adaptive AI tools remain underexplored in the Nigerian secondary school context, particularly in Northern Nigeria. There is still little empirical evidence on how such platforms influence self-efficacy and problem-solving in environments marked by large class sizes, scarce resources, and inconsistent ICT infrastructure. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by investigating the effectiveness of AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction in improving students' confidence and problem-solving performance in Northern Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design of the pre-test, post-test, non-

randomized control group type, using intact classes. The study was conducted in the Zaria Education Zone of Kaduna State, Nigeria, where secondary school students often have limited access to innovative instructional technologies.

The target population comprised all Senior Secondary II (SSII) students in public co-educational secondary schools within the zone. The sample consisted of 180 students (90 in the experimental group and 90 in the control group) drawn from four purposively selected schools. Selection was based on the availability of ICT infrastructure and willingness to participate. In the experimental group, algebra lessons were delivered using an AI-powered adaptive learning platform (e.g., Squirrel AI or a locally customized AI-based application), whereas the control group was taught using conventional instructional methods.

Two instruments were employed for data collection:

Algebra Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES) – adapted from Bandura's self-efficacy model.

Algebra Problem-Solving Test (APST) – developed to assess students' algebraic problem-solving skills. Both instruments were subjected to validation by experts in mathematics education and instructional technology. A pilot test conducted in a neighboring school (excluded from the main study) established the reliability indices of the instruments, yielding coefficients of 0.81 (ASES, Cronbach's alpha) and 0.76 (APST, KR-20). For data analysis, descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize responses, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to determine the effect of the treatment after adjusting for initial group differences. All

statistical tests were carried out at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Data Analysis

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in self-efficacy scores between students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Self-Efficacy Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Pre-Test Mean (SD)	Post-Test Mean (SD)
Experimental Group	90	42.18 (5.74)	79.24 (6.21)
Control Group	90	41.87 (5.63)	61.03 (6.88)

Interpretation:

Table 1 shows a noticeable increase in self-efficacy scores among students in the experimental group who received adaptive instruction powered by AI. While both groups had similar pre-test means, the post-test mean of the experimental group was substantially higher (79.24) than that of the control group (61.03),

suggesting a positive effect of the AI-based instructional strategy on students' self-beliefs

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy scores of students taught algebra using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Table 2: ANCOVA Result on Students' Self-Efficacy Scores

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Partial η ²
Covariate (Pre-Test)	524.14	1	524.14	9.42	.003	.049
Group	2162.32	1	2162.32	38.89	<.001	.180
Error	9784.41	176	55.59			
Total	-	180	-			

Interpretation:

After controlling for pre-test scores, the ANCOVA results presented in Table 2 reveal a statistically significant difference in self-efficacy scores between the experimental and control groups, $F(1,176) = 38.89, p < .001$. The effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.180$) demonstrates a large practical impact, indicating that students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction experienced substantial improvements in algebra self-

efficacy compared to those taught through conventional methods. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) is rejected.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in algebraic problem-solving performance between students exposed to AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught Through conventional methods?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Problem-Solving Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Pre-Test Mean (SD)	Post-Test Mean (SD)
Experimental Group	90	18.67 (3.44)	36.48 (4.11)
Control Group	90	18.24 (3.57)	27.31 (4.90)

Interpretation:

Table 3 shows a notable improvement in the algebraic problem-solving performance of the experimental group, with the post-test mean increasing to 36.48 compared to 27.31 for the control group. This suggests a considerable effect on enhancing students' problem-solving abilities in algebra.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught using AI-powered adaptive instruction and those taught using conventional methods.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result on Algebraic Problem-Solving Performance

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	Partial η^2
Covariate (Pre-Test)	287.83	1	287.83	11.62	.001	.062
Group	3087.19	1	3087.19	74.63	<.001	.298
Error	7288.51	176	41.42			
Total	-	180	-			

Interpretation:

The ANCOVA results in Table 4 show a statistically significant difference in the algebraic problem-solving performance of students taught with AI-based instruction compared to those taught through conventional methods, $F(1,176) = 74.63, p < .001$. The effect size (partial $\eta^2 = .298$) represents a very large practical impact, confirming that the AI-powered intervention substantially enhanced students' problem-solving abilities. This evidence demonstrates that adaptive AI instruction is not only statistically effective but also pedagogically meaningful in improving algebraic learning outcomes. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₂) is rejected.

significant and positive effect on students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in Northern Nigerian secondary schools. Evidence from Tables 1 and 2 shows that students exposed to adaptive AI-based instruction demonstrated greater improvements in self-efficacy than those taught using conventional methods. This supports Bandura's (1997) proposition that mastery experiences and constructive feedback reinforce students' beliefs in their academic competence. In this study, the platform's capacity to provide individualized scaffolding and immediate corrective feedback likely played a central role in bolstering students' confidence to engage productively with algebraic tasks. These findings align with Heffernan and Heffernan (2014), who reported that intelligent tutoring

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study revealed that AI-powered adaptive algebra instruction had a

systems enhance learners' confidence in studying mathematics independently.

Similarly, results associated with the second hypothesis, presented in Tables 3 and 4, revealed a statistically significant improvement in students' algebraic problem-solving skills following exposure to AI-powered adaptive instruction. The large effect size indicates not only statistical significance but also strong practical relevance, suggesting that such interventions can produce substantial classroom-level benefits. This finding corroborates Aliyu et al. (2025), who observed that adaptive learning technologies improved both engagement and achievement in mathematics problem-solving. It also resonates with Adeleke et al., (2025), who demonstrated that Nigerian students receiving stepwise adaptive feedback achieved higher levels of accuracy and confidence when solving mathematical problems.

A notable strength of this study lies in its dual focus on self-efficacy and problem-solving, two interrelated constructs central to mathematics achievement but often underexplored in conventional instructional approaches. The integration of personalized pacing, timely intervention, and continuous feedback provided by the AI system likely fostered deeper conceptual understanding and improved retention. These findings are also consistent with Sweller's (1988) Cognitive Load Theory, which emphasizes minimizing extraneous cognitive demands to optimize working memory and enhance learning efficiency.

Beyond theoretical contributions, the study adds to the local evidence base by offering context-specific insights into the potential of AI in mathematics education within rural and

underserved Northern Nigerian schools. Given the systemic challenges in these setting including overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, and uneven teacher expertise the use of AI-powered systems provides a promising pathway toward scalable, cost-effective, and data-driven instructional support.

In summary, the significant gains in both self-efficacy and problem-solving performance documented in this study strengthen the case for incorporating AI-powered adaptive systems into mathematics instruction in Nigerian secondary schools. These findings not only affirm international research but also underscore the urgent need for national educational policy and infrastructural investment to enable digital transformation and foster equitable access to innovative learning technologies.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered adaptive instruction significantly enhances students' self-efficacy and problem-solving performance in algebra. Unlike the traditional teacher-centered methods prevalent in many Nigerian classrooms, the AI-based approach offered a learner-centered, flexible, and interactive environment that dynamically adapted to students' individual learning needs. The experimental group consistently outperformed the control group, with large effect sizes indicating that the intervention not only improved achievement but also meaningfully strengthened students' confidence in their mathematical abilities.

The findings provide strong empirical evidence for the integration of AI technologies into the secondary mathematics

curriculum, particularly in contexts such as Northern Nigeria where persistent challenges—limited resources, overcrowded classrooms, and teacher shortages—hamper effective instruction. By demonstrating measurable improvements in both affective (self-efficacy) and cognitive (problem-solving) outcomes, this study affirms that leveraging AI-based adaptive learning can serve as a transformative pedagogical strategy for bridging performance gaps and reimagining mathematics education in underserved environments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Integration of AI into the Mathematics Curriculum: The Federal and State Ministries of Education should facilitate the integration of adaptive AI-powered learning platforms into the senior secondary school mathematics curriculum. Such integration will promote personalized learning and significantly enhance students' academic achievement.
- Teacher Training and Capacity Building: Mathematics teachers should undergo continuous professional development on the effective use and management of AI-powered platforms. Equipping teachers with these skills will ensure that the pedagogical potential of AI is maximized.
- Infrastructure Investment: Governments and educational stakeholders should prioritize investment in ICT infrastructure, particularly in underserved and rural schools. This includes providing access to devices, stable internet connectivity, and

functional digital learning environments to support AI-enabled instruction.

- Further Research: Additional studies should be carried out across other mathematics topics, different school types, and various educational zones. Longitudinal research is also recommended to examine the long-term effects of AI integration on students' learning outcomes, attitudes, and retention.
- Public-Private Partnerships: Strong collaboration should be fostered between government agencies, EdTech companies, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to provide affordable AI-based tools. Pilot programs and subsidized initiatives can help ensure equitable access in low-resource schools.

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